

A dynamic state of space gives the notion of a discrete (quantum) system

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A hypothesis on space is described here. Based on this hypothesis, dynamics of a cluster of quantized (discrete) areas of space has been made responsible for the notion of a discrete (quantum) system. An innovative approach named area-time approach for a discrete (quantum) system is expressed. The wave function of a discrete (quantum) system is derived from the discrete areas dynamics of that system. Distribution of mass, momentum, and energy in a discrete system are illustrated according to this approach. Redshift due to expansion of the universe, thermal De Broglie wavelength, gravitation, redshift due to gravitation, black hole and wave-particle duality are explained according to the proposal.

I. INTRODUCTION

In his paper published in 1905 Albert Einstein stated electromagnetic radiation as electromagnetic state of space [1,2].

We know that for an inertial reference frame $\frac{dx}{dt}$ is a constant and for a non-inertial reference frame $\frac{dx}{dt}$ is a variable; where, x is the distance travelled by a reference frame and t is the required time for that travel. Distance is a property of space. According to the theory of special relativity, local time should be measured by an event chain that happened in local space [3,4].

The laws of physics fall into two categories. (1) Laws valid only at inertial reference frame. The laws of Newtonian mechanics and special relativity fall in this category. (2) Laws valid at non-inertial reference frame and also at inertial reference frame with approximation. Laws of general relativity fall in this category.

According to special relativity if a clock comes back to its initial location after a travel through space, then it shows a lagging time compared to a stationary clock at that location [3,4].

The above classification and special theory of relativity indicate that character of movement of a substance through space is a fundamental issue.

Albert Einstein said, "It followed from the special theory of relativity that mass and energy are both but different manifestations of the same thing – a somewhat unfamiliar conception for the average mind. Furthermore, the equation E is equal to m c -squared, in which energy is put equal to mass, multiplied by the square of the velocity of light, showed that very small amounts of mass may be converted into a very large amount of energy and vice versa. The mass and energy were in fact equivalent, according to the formula mentioned above. This was demonstrated by Cockcroft and Walton in 1932, experimentally" [5].

"The same thing" of the above statement indicates a general but fundamental element.

In the theory of general relativity A. Einstein expressed gravitation as the curvature of spacetime [6,7].

Accepting all indications mentioned above we take a step forward by considering 'space' as a fundamental element. In this paper quantum (discrete) nature of space is accepted [8]. Dynamics of a cluster of quantized (discrete) areas of space has been made responsible for the notion of a quantum (discrete) system.

Here is an attempt to figure out the background philosophy of a quantum (discrete) system.

II. HYPOTHESIS

There is a dynamic vector \vec{A} in the space which represents discrete (quantized) area of space. In a region of space, the number of \vec{A} is finite.

Dynamics of a cluster of these discrete areas of space is the source of wave function of a quantum (discrete) system. It means a quantum system is a special state of space.

In such a quantum system local time is a non-physical and discrete (quantized) entity.

In that quantum system there is a non-zero finite ratio as bellow-

$$\frac{\frac{d\vec{A}}{dt}}{\frac{d\vec{A}}{dx}} = R \quad (1)$$

Where, $\frac{d\vec{A}}{dt}$ is a quantity in time domain and its value depends on the dynamics of local space, $\frac{d\vec{A}}{dx}$ is a quantity in space domain in x direction and its value depend on the dynamics of local space.

For a stable quantum system there must be a period in the dynamics of \vec{A} . We know that any periodic entity can be represented by its phase dynamics. So, we can re-write equation no.(1) as bellow-

$$R = \frac{\frac{d\vec{A}}{dt}}{\frac{d\vec{A}}{dx}} = \frac{2\pi}{T} = \frac{\omega}{k} \quad (2)$$

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Where, T is period in time domain, λ is period in space domain, ω is angular frequency in time domain and k is angular frequency in space domain.

Unit of $\frac{\omega}{k}$ is ms^{-1} . So, $\frac{d\vec{A}/dt}{d\vec{A}/dx}$ is the phase velocity of \vec{A} and we want to declare that it is equal to the speed of light c .

In this paper, a quantum system's area is the quantized (discrete) area of space.

III. $\Psi(x, t)$ IS RELATED TO A PHYSICAL ENTITY

We know that in a quantum system for positive x direction Schrodinger wave function generator is-

$$\Psi_g(x, t) = Ae^{i(kx - \omega t)} \quad (3)$$

$\Psi_g(x, t)$ represents clockwise rotating vectors at various positions of space. Magnitude, phase (angle) change per unit time (angular frequency of generated wave), phase (angle) change per unit length (wave number of generated wave) of these vectors are A, ω, k . For a particular x , $\Psi_g(x, t)$ shows different directions of rotating vector for different t . For a particular t , $\Psi_g(x, t)$ shows different directions of rotating vector for different x .

Schrodinger wave is a traveling wave in the form of sinusoidal or co-sinusoidal or any other form depending on the dynamics of rotating vectors for a complete cycle. This traveling wave is also the de Broglie wave of this quantum system. We consider here a generated simple sinusoidal wave form for Schrodinger wave in positive x direction and it is-

$$\Psi(x, t) = A \sin(kx - \omega t) \quad (4)$$

We want to declare $\Psi(x, t) = A \sin(kx - \omega t)$ as the basic Schrodinger wave. So, it is the Schrodinger wave of a basic discrete (quantum) system.

In our discussion we consider an ideal local situation. So, phase velocity of the generated wave $\Psi(x, t)$ is $v = \frac{\omega}{k} = f\lambda$. Where, f is time domain frequency ($f = 1/T$), λ is space domain period (wavelength) of $A \sin(kx - \omega t)$.

Suppose N number simultaneously rotating vectors create a complete cycle of $\Psi(x, t)$. So, we can say that N number of rotating vectors make a cluster. Distance (d) between any two adjacent rotating vectors of a cluster contributes to wavelength (λ) of that cluster. It means-

$$\lambda = (N - 1) \times d \quad (5)$$

Hence, d influences k . We consider here the ideal local situation. So, d influences ω linearly.

If d increases then λ increase and k, ω, f decrease. If d decreases then λ decrease and k, ω, f increase.

It should be noted here that d necessarily is not a distance between any two physically adjacent areas of space. It is a distance between any two areas of space which participate in creating the Schrodinger wave and adjacent in space domain Schrodinger wave.

In traditional quantum mechanics we defined $\Psi(x, t)$ (also $\Psi_g(x, t)$) as a dimensionless entity intentionally so that we can use it freely with Planck constant in various operators. For this reason, operators had to design carefully to give proper dimension to an observable. No doubt it is a nice technique. But that is not the only way to present a quantum physical system. Later we will see a different approach.

Now we want to ask the same old question. Is it possible by a wave function to stand for a physical quantum system without being related to a physical entity of that system? Our answer is *no*. As $\Psi(x, t)$ (means $\Psi_g(x, t)$) represents a quantum physical system, it must be related to a dynamic physical entity of that system.

Our target is to relate $\Psi_g(x, t) = Ae^{i(kx - \omega t)}$ with the moving quantized (discrete) areas at various positions in the quantum system and to relate $\Psi(x, t) = A \sin(kx - \omega t)$ with the discretely changing area in x direction (reference direction) in the quantum system.

We will keep in mind the finite single value character of $\Psi(x, t)$.

IV. DYNAMICS OF AREA IN A QUANTUM SYSTEM

Suppose in a quantum system Y , N number areas create a cluster C . In that cluster distance between any two adjacent areas is d and they are in a close line (close quantum system) or in open line (open quantum system). These areas are represented by \vec{D}_n where, $n = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, N$ and n indicates n^{th} area. All $|\vec{D}_n|$ are equal suppose, $|\vec{D}_n| = A$. So, in the cluster C of that quantum system the number of simultaneous movements is N .

But each area has a peer area having opposite direction. So, in Y quantum system there are more N number areas which create peer cluster C' . They can be represented by \vec{D}'_n where, $n = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, N$ and n indicates n^{th} area. All $|\vec{D}'_n|$ are equal suppose, $|\vec{D}'_n| = A$. So, in the cluster C' of that quantum system the number of simultaneous movements is N .

In fact, $|\vec{D}_n| = |\vec{D}'_n| = A$.

In the next parts of this section, we will study the dynamics of \vec{D}_n and \vec{D}'_n and show that these dynamics can explain mass, momentum (both linear and angular), energy of that quantum system and their discrete nature.

A. $\Psi(x, t)$ is changing area in x direction

In a direction area can be changed by two processes. (a) Due to rotation of area (b) Due to vibration of area. In this subsection we will derive $\Psi(x, t)$ due to the mentioned process.

1. $\Psi(x, t)$ due to rotation of area

In row 1 of *FIG.IV.1* the first one is a schematic figure for a single area \vec{D}_1 at $x = 0$ of cluster C and the second one is for all areas of both clusters.

Row 2-4 in *FIG.IV.1* are schematic figures in time domain for a single area \vec{D}_1 at $x = 0$ of cluster C .

Row 5-7 in *FIG.IV.1* are schematic figures in space domain for different areas at $t = 0$ of cluster C . We indicate here only five areas of cluster C . They are the first one \vec{D}_1 and intermediate three \vec{D}_{i_1} , \vec{D}_{i_2} , \vec{D}_{i_3} and the last one \vec{D}_N .

The first figure of the first row represents a rotating area and position of us. We see clockwise rotation. The second figure of first row represents peer clusters.

The second row shows the direction of rotation. Changing areas are positive if they have positive projections towards our right-side direction and negative if they have negative projections towards our right-side direction. It means towards our right-side direction is the reference direction (x direction). We consider a rotating vector for change of \vec{D}_1 .

The third row shows corresponding rotating vector. Red one for moving area $\Psi_{gD_1}(t) = Ae^{-i\omega t}$. It rotates clockwise.

The fourth row shows corresponding wave in time domain in reference direction (x direction). Dotted red wave represents changing area $\Psi_{D_1}(t) = A \sin(\omega t)$ in time domain in reference direction (x direction).

Similarly, we have $\Psi_{gD_2}(t) \dots \Psi_{gD_n}(t)$ having constant phase difference among them and $\Psi_{D_2}(t) \dots \Psi_{D_n}(t)$ having constant phase difference among them. Phase difference is ensured by kx .

Now, in cluster C we have N number rotating vectors. They are $\Psi_{gD_1}(t) \dots \Psi_{gD_n}(t)$. Suppose two adjacent rotating vectors are at x_1 and x_2 . Then phase difference between them is $k \times (x_2 - x_1)$. As distance between any two adjacent area in cluster C is constant, phase difference between any two adjacent $\Psi_{gD}(t)$ is also constant. In that case all localized rotating vectors for all areas of cluster C means all $\Psi_{gD}(t)$ ($\Psi_{gD_1}(t) \dots \Psi_{gD_n}(t)$) can be replaced by a single expression like $\Psi_g(x, t) = Ae^{i(kx - \omega t)}$. Here, $\Psi_g(x, t)$ represents all rotating vectors for all moving areas of cluster C of physical quantum system Y .

$\Psi_D(t)$ is a wave generated by $\Psi_{gD}(t)$. So, due to the same logic there is also a single expression like $\Psi(x, t) = A \sin(kx - \omega t)$, which replaced all $\Psi_D(t)$ ($\Psi_{D_1}(t) \dots \Psi_{D_n}(t)$).

This $\Psi(x, t) = A \sin(kx - \omega t)$ is the Schrodinger wave of cluster C of that quantum system Y towards reference direction (x direction). It is also the de Broglie wave of cluster C of that quantum system Y towards reference direction (x direction).

Discrete space area indicates no area in every point of space domain. In a quantum system there is a distance d between any two adjacent area location in space domain. Hence, our proposed Schrodinger wave is discrete (dotted) in the space domain.

On the other hand, there is a time gap t_g between any two sequential angular movements of an area. Hence, our proposed Schrodinger wave is discrete (dotted) in the time domain.

According to our hypothesis, angular movement of an area is not continuous but discrete, meaning in a quantum (discrete) system an area of space can angularly move only in a discrete angle θ_d .

These d , t_g and θ_d are responsible for discrete values of mass, momentum (both linear and angular) and energy of a quantum (discrete) system.

Hence, we can say that periodic rotation of areas of space can give the notion of a quantum (discrete) system.

2. $\Psi(x, t)$ due to vibration of area

In row 1 of *FIG.IV.2* the first one is a schematic figure for a single area \vec{D}_1 at $x = 0$ of cluster C and the second one is for all areas of both clusters.

Row 2-4 in *FIG.IV.2* are schematic figures in time domain for a single area \vec{D}_1 at $x = 0$ of cluster C .

Row 5-7 in *FIG.IV.2* are schematic figures in space domain for different areas at $t = 0$ of cluster C . We indicate here only five areas of cluster C . They are the first one \vec{D}_1 and intermediate three \vec{D}_{i_1} , \vec{D}_{i_2} , \vec{D}_{i_3} and the last one \vec{D}_N .

The first figure of the first row represents a vibrating area and position of us. We see clockwise and anticlockwise movement (vibration) of an area. The second figure of first row represents peer clusters.

The second row shows the direction of movement. Changing areas are positive if they have positive projections towards our right-side direction and negative if they have negative projections towards our right-side direction. It means towards our right-side direction is the reference direction (x direction). We consider a rotating vector for change of \vec{D}_1 .

The third row shows corresponding rotating vector. Red one for moving area $\Psi_{gD_1}(t) = Ae^{-i\omega t}$. It rotates clockwise.

The fourth row shows corresponding wave in time domain in reference direction (x direction). Dotted red wave represents changing area $\Psi_{D_1}(t) = A \sin(\omega t)$ in time domain in reference direction (x direction).

Similarly, we have $\Psi_{gD_2}(t) \dots \Psi_{gD_n}(t)$ having constant phase difference among them and

FIG. IV.1. For rotation of area (schematic)

FIG. IV.2. For vibration of area (schematic)

$\Psi_{D_2}(t).....\Psi_{D_n}(t)$ having constant phase difference among them. Phase difference is ensured by kx .

Now, in cluster C we have N number rotating vectors. They are $\Psi_{gD_1}(t).....\Psi_{gD_n}(t)$. Suppose two adjacent rotating vectors are at x_1 and x_2 . Then phase difference between them is $k \times (x_2 - x_1)$. As distance between any two adjacent area in cluster C is constant, phase difference between any two adjacent $\Psi_{gD}(t)$ is also constant. In that case all localized rotating vectors for all areas of cluster C means all $\Psi_{gD}(t)$ ($\Psi_{gD_1}(t).....\Psi_{gD_n}(t)$) can be replaced by a single expression like $\Psi_g(x, t) = Ae^{i(kx - \omega t)}$. Here, $\Psi_g(x, t)$ represents all rotating vectors for all moving areas of cluster C of physical quantum system Y .

$\Psi_D(t)$ is a wave generated by $\Psi_{gD}(t)$. So, due to the same logic there is also a single expression like $\Psi(x, t) = A \sin(kx - \omega t)$, which replaced all $\Psi_D(t)$ ($\Psi_{D_1}(t).....\Psi_{D_n}(t)$).

This $\Psi(x, t) = A \sin(kx - \omega t)$ is the Schrodinger wave of cluster C of that quantum system Y towards reference direction (x direction). It is also the de Broglie wave of cluster C of that quantum system Y towards reference direction (x direction).

Discrete space area indicates no area in every point of space domain. In a quantum system there is a distance d between any two adjacent area location in space domain. Hence, our proposed Schrodinger wave is discrete (dotted) in the space domain.

On the other hand, there is a time gap t_g between any two sequential angular movements of an area. Hence, our proposed Schrodinger wave is discrete (dotted) in the time domain.

According to our hypothesis, angular movement of an area is not continuous but discrete, meaning in a quantum (discrete) system an area of space can angularly move only in a discrete angle θ_d .

These d, t_g and θ_d are responsible for discrete values of mass, momentum (both linear and angular) and energy of a quantum (discrete) system.

Hence, we can say that periodic vibration of areas of space can give the notion of a quantum (discrete) system.

B. Dynamics of a cluster of areas in a discrete system

Here we treat the projection scenario of areas in the reference direction (x direction) as the state of those areas (discrete system). We know that inertia of a system works against any change of that system state.

For two different discrete systems, in the same reference direction (x direction), for equal change of area there need two different time duration and during equal time duration the change of area are different.

Now, we want to declare a relation among inertia (Numeric measure of which is mass) M , change of areas ΔA in the reference direction and needed time duration Δt for that areas change.

The relation is-

$$M \propto \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta A} \quad (6)$$

or,

$$M = bZ \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta A} \quad (7)$$

or,

$$Z = \frac{M}{b} \times \frac{\Delta A}{\Delta t} \quad (8)$$

Where,

b is a unit less constant depending on the style of angular movement (rotation/vibration or their combination) of areas.

In SI unit, Z has the unit of $Kg.m^2.s^{-1}$ which is the unit of reduced Planck constant \hbar . Hence, we have another declaration that Z is nothing but the reduced Planck constant \hbar .

Now, we want to rearrange equation no. (7) as-

$$M = b\hbar \frac{1}{\frac{\Delta A}{\Delta t}} \quad (9)$$

The denominator $\frac{\Delta A}{\Delta t}$ of equation no. (9) is the time rate of area change in the reference direction (x direction). So, M is inversely proportional to $\frac{\Delta A}{\Delta t}$.

In such a discrete system $\Delta t, \Delta A$ must be quantized and non-zero and finite.

In such a discrete system for any two adjacent events (angular movement of areas), states must be different in the reference direction (x direction). This statement is valid for both time domain and space domain.

C. Mass, energy and momentum distribution in a discrete system

According to our proposal, basic Schrodinger wave $\Psi(x, t) = A \sin(kx - \omega t)$.

To get a distribution m having Kg unit in a discrete system we must make an operation on $\Psi(x, t) = A \sin(kx - \omega t)$ as below-

$$m = b\hbar \frac{1}{\frac{\partial [A \sin(kx - \omega t)]}{\partial t}} \quad (10)$$

$$m = b\hbar \frac{1}{-\omega A \cos(kx - \omega t)} \quad (11)$$

$$m = -\frac{b\hbar T}{4\pi^2 A} \sec(kx - \omega t) \quad (12)$$

To get a distribution E having $Kg.m^2.s^{-2}$ unit in a discrete system we must make an operation on $\Psi(x, t) = A \sin(kx - \omega t)$ as below-

$$E = b\hbar \frac{1}{\frac{\partial[A \sin(kx - \omega t)]}{\partial t}} \times \frac{\partial^2[A \sin(kx - \omega t)]}{\partial t^2} \quad (13)$$

$$E = \frac{b\hbar}{T} \tan(kx - \omega t) \quad (14)$$

To get a distribution p having $Kg.m.s^{-1}$ unit in a discrete system we must make an operation on $\Psi(x, t) = A \sin(kx - \omega t)$ as below-

$$p = b\hbar \frac{1}{\frac{\partial[A \sin(kx - \omega t)]}{\partial t}} \times \left[\frac{\partial^2[A \sin(kx - \omega t)]}{\partial x \partial t} \right] \quad (15)$$

$$p = -\frac{b\hbar}{\lambda} \tan(kx - \omega t) \quad (16)$$

Hence, we can declare $b\hbar \frac{1}{\frac{\partial}{\partial t}}$ as mass operator, $b\hbar \frac{1}{\frac{\partial}{\partial t}} \times \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}$ as energy operator, $b\hbar \frac{1}{\frac{\partial}{\partial t}} \times \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial t}$ as linear momentum operator for the basic Schrodinger wave equation.

According to our hypothesis, a surface gives spin angular momentum by its angular movement. Now, we want to define the spin angular momentum s as bellow-

$$s = m \times q \quad (17)$$

Where,

m is distributed mass in a discrete system due to angular movement of areas of space.

q is distributed angular speed of space area measured in $m^2.s^{-1}$ unit in the reference speed direction (x direction)

So, according to our hypothesis and definition, spin angular momentum,

$$s = b\hbar \frac{1}{\frac{\partial[A \sin(kx - \omega t)]}{\partial t}} \times \frac{\partial[A \sin(kx - \omega t)]}{\partial t} = b\hbar \quad (18)$$

For peer basic Schrodinger wave $\Psi(x, t) = -A \sin(kx - \omega t)$ and

$$m = \frac{b\hbar T}{4\pi^2 A} \sec(kx - \omega t) \quad (19)$$

$$E = \frac{b\hbar}{T} \tan(kx - \omega t) \quad (20)$$

$$p = -\frac{b\hbar}{\lambda} \tan(kx - \omega t) \quad (21)$$

FIG. IV.3. Basic Schrodinger wave pair in time domain (schematic)

$$s = b\hbar \quad (22)$$

Here, we want to draw the Schrodinger wave, mass wave, energy wave and momentum wave for both cluster C and C' in time domain and in space domain. In these figures (*FIG.IV.3–12*) unprimed waves belong to cluster C and primed waves belong to cluster C' .

1. Mass, energy and momentum distribution in a discrete system in time domain

Firstly, for a fixed position in space domain we want to draw Schrodinger wave, mass wave, energy wave and momentum wave in time domain.

In the reference direction (x direction) effective time domain period of Schrodinger wave pair becomes half ($T/2$) of the original (T).

Conventional unit less time domain Schrodinger wave $\Psi(t)$ gives the probability of finding a particle in time domain by $|\Psi(t)|^2$. Period of $|\Psi(t)|^2$ is half of period of $|\Psi(t)|$.

From the view of time domain period, our proposed effective time domain Schrodinger wave pair towards the reference direction (x direction) is compatible to conventional $|\Psi(t)|^2$.

It is clearly seen that in the reference direction (x direction) time domain period of mass wave, energy wave and linear momentum wave are also $T/2$ but spin angular momentum in time domain is a constant.

2. Mass, energy and momentum distribution in a discrete system in space domain

Secondly, for a fixed position in the time domain we want to draw Schrodinger wave, mass wave, energy wave and momentum wave in space domain.

FIG. IV.4. Basic Shrodinger wave pair and mass distribution in time domain (schematic)

FIG. IV.7. Basic Shrodinger wave pair and spin angular momentum distribution in time domain (schematic)

FIG. IV.5. Basic Shrodinger wave pair and energy distribution in time domain (schematic)

FIG. IV.8. Basic Shrodinger wave pair in space domain (schematic)

FIG. IV.6. Basic Shrodinger wave pair and linear momentum distribution in time domain (schematic)

In the reference direction (x direction) effective space domain period of Schrodinger wave pair becomes half ($\lambda/2$) of the original (λ).

Conventional unit less space domain Schrodinger wave $\Psi(x)$ gives the probability of finding a particle in space domain by $|\Psi(x)|^2$. Period of $|\Psi(x)|^2$ is half of period of $|\Psi(x)|$.

From the view of space domain period, our proposed effective space domain Schrodinger wave pair towards the reference direction (x direction) is compatible to conventional $|\Psi(x)|^2$.

It is clearly seen that in the reference direction (x direction) space domain period of mass wave, energy wave and linear momentum wave are also $\lambda/2$ but spin angular momentum in space domain is a constant.

FIG. IV.9. Basic Shrodinger wave pair and mass distribution in space domain (schematic)

FIG. IV.12. Basic Shrodinger wave pair and spin angular momentum distribution in space domain (schematic)

FIG. IV.10. Basic Shrodinger wave pair and energy distribution in space domain (schematic)

FIG. IV.11. Basic Shrodinger wave pair and linear momentum distribution in space domain (schematic)

3. General discussion for space and time domain distributions

According to our hypothesis, for both time domain and space domain, in a discrete system for any two adjacent events (angular movement of area/areas), states must be different in the reference direction (ΔA and Δt are quantized and non-zero and finite). Hence, operators give finite values.

We see that according to our hypothesis there is a pair of clusters of areas in a quantum system. Hence there is a pair of Schrodinger waves in a basic discrete (quantum) system. These waves are peer to each other and phase difference between them is π .

D. Superposition and reduction of states

Projections of a steady still area in different angular directions from its normal are different. So, if an observer does not know from which angular direction, he/she must measure the area or if an observer is free to measure the area from any angular direction, then every possible projected area has an equal probability to be measured by him/her. To the observer it is a superposition of the projected areas on the position of steady still area.

By deciding a particular measuring angular direction, a particular value of projected area theoretically becomes fixed. It means if we measure from that angular direction, we will find that fixed value. We will not find any other values which were probable before deciding the measuring angle. Due to the decision on measuring angle situation becomes from superposition to a particular one to the observer, theoretically and experimentally.

In other way, if that area is not steady still but dynamic then for a fixed positioned observer the measuring angular direction depends on the dynamics of the area. A particular measuring angular direction has a particu-

lar probability depending on the associated Schrodinger wave of that area. This associated Schrodinger wave depends on the dynamics of that area. So, to be measured a particular value of the projected area has a particular probability. To the fixed positioned observer, it is a superposition of the projected areas on the position of dynamic area.

When a measurement (interaction) happened, a single value of projected area is found, particularly for that measuring angle. Any other values of projected area which were probable before interaction will not be found. Due to the interaction (measurement) on a single measuring angle situation becomes from superposition to a particular one to the fixed positioned observer, theoretically and experimentally.

According to our hypothesis, the state of a quantum system is nothing but in a reference direction (x direction) the projection scenario of the dynamic areas of that system.

To be super positioned states must exist in a single position in space domain and in a single position in time domain. According to our hypothesis, a quantum system having finite and discrete and dynamic structure cannot have such states which are in a single position in space domain and in a single position in time domain.

So, according to our hypothesis, in a quantum system traditional superposition situation does not exist physically.

If due to areas movement of a discrete system, in the reference direction (x direction) there is not a single traveling sinusoidal wave but a combination of traveling sinusoidal waves (found by Fourier transformation) then that discrete system can be called as a compound discrete system. The Schrodinger wave of a compound discrete system is-

$$\Psi(x, t) = \Psi_1(x, t) + \Psi_2(x, t) + \Psi_3(x, t) + \dots \quad (23)$$

Where,

$\Psi(x, t)$ is the Schrodinger wave of a compound discrete system.

$\Psi_1(x, t)$, $\Psi_2(x, t)$, $\Psi_3(x, t)$ etc. are the Schrodinger wave of basic discrete (quantum) system.

λ_1 is space domain period and T_1 is time domain period of $\Psi_1(x, t)$.

λ_2 is space domain period and T_2 is time domain period of $\Psi_2(x, t)$.

λ_3 is space domain period and T_3 is time domain period of $\Psi_3(x, t)$.

In a compound discrete system there may be $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda_3 = \dots$ and $T_1 = T_2 = T_3 = \dots$.

So, a compound discrete system may be treated as theoretical superposition of some basic discrete systems.

E. Investigation for different d

Any radiation is an open quantum system, which means wave of this system spread in space. Any so-called particle is a closed quantum system which means the wave of this system travels in a loop in space.

According to our hypothesis, in a quantum system a cluster of quantized areas creates a complete cycle of wave. In a cluster; number of quantized areas N , distance between two adjacent areas d (as per definition of d), phase difference per unit time ω , phase difference per unit length k , style parameter b are characteristic parameters of that cluster. \hbar is the cluster value of a cluster which is same (constant) for all clusters.

For an ideal local space (vacuum, where there is no other quantum system), if d decreases in a cluster then according to the equation no.(5), space domain period λ decreases and according to $c = \omega/k = f\lambda$ time domain frequency f increases.

In vacuum speed of photon stream (an open quantum system) is fixed ($c = \omega/k = f\lambda$). In a fixed length of photon stream cluster number is high for high frequency.

It means in a fixed length of photon stream number of cluster having cluster constant \hbar is high for high frequency. So, all these clusters inside this length of photon streams of different frequency need the same time to impact on a sensor. Because the speed of photon stream of different frequency is same, and it is c . Hence, we find more impacts for high frequency than low frequency. A greater number of impacts means more energy.

This analysis compatible to $E = hf$.

Like an open quantum system (here photon stream) a close quantum system (so called particle) also can be explained.

So according to our hypothesis-

$$E \propto \frac{1}{d} \quad (24)$$

F. Space-time is 'the same thing' of Einstein

According to the above discussion mass and energy are different manifestations of the area-time. Hence, it can be said here that the term 'the same thing' in the comment of Einstein [7] is nothing but the 'area-time' (space-time).

V. EXPLANATION OF SOME PHYSICAL ISSUES

A. Redshift due to expansion of the universe

In FIG.V.1 two source S_1 and S_2 emit light (open quantum system) at the same moment t_0 toward right hand direction. The wavelength of emitted light is λ_0 for

FIG. V.1. for redshift

both sources. A wave w_1 needs t_1 sec to travel from S_1 to the screen. A wave w_2 needs t_2 sec to travel from S_2 to the screen.

Here, x_2 , x_1 are distances at cosmological scale and $x_2 \gg x_1$. So, $t_2 \gg t_1$

According to Hubble's law w_2 faces more space expansion than w_1 to reach the screen. Suppose Δx_2 is the measure of space expansion in the path of w_2 and Δx_1 is the measure of space expansion in the path of w_1 . So, according to Hubble's law $\Delta x_2 \gg \Delta x_1$.

Δx says that there is an increment in physical distance between any two adjacent areas of space and hence, Δx also says increment in d of a quantum system.

So, due to Δx_2 there is Δd_2 for cluster of w_2 and due to Δx_1 there is Δd_1 for cluster of w_1 . Before hitting w_2 on the screen d of the cluster of w_2 becomes to $d + \Delta d_2 = d_2$. Before hitting w_1 on the screen d of the cluster of w_1 becomes to $d + \Delta d_1 = d_1$.

As $\Delta x_2 \gg \Delta x_1$, $d_2 \gg d_1$. Again as $d_2 \gg d_1$, $\lambda_2 \gg \lambda_1$ where, λ_2 and λ_1 are the respective wavelength of w_2 and w_1 before their hits on the screen.

Due to $c = f\lambda$, $f_1 \gg f_2$ where, f_2 and f_1 are the respective frequency of w_2 and w_1 before their hits on the screen.

B. Thermal De Broglie wavelength

Suppose a quantum system Y is in an ideal local space (vacuum, where no other quantum system is). We know that the thermal De Broglie wavelength of Y is-

$$\lambda_{th} = \frac{h}{\sqrt{3mK_B T}} \quad (25)$$

Let us explain equation no. (25) according to our proposal.

We know that if temperature T increases then oscillation in a quantum system also increases. Increasing Oscillation means the number of area movements increases per unit time in time domain. It indicates an increment of number of complete cycles of area movement per unit time in time domain. Final indication is the increment of frequency f means ω of De Broglie wave of that quantum system. Hence, according to $E = hf = \frac{3}{2}K_B T$, energy

of that quantum system increases. Then according to equation no. (2), k also increases. Increment of k means decrease of λ_{th} . But according to the equation no. (5) decrease of λ_{th} occurred by decreasing of adjacent area distance d in that quantum system. So, we see that by increasing temperature of a quantum system, its energy increases but size (volume) decreases.

Now, if the temperature T of Y decreases then oscillation in Y also decreases. Oscillation decreasing means number of area movement decreases per unit time in time domain. It indicates a reduction of the number of complete cycles of area movement per unit time in time domain. Final indication is the reduction of frequency f means ω of De Broglie wave of that quantum system. Hence, according to $E = hf = \frac{3}{2}K_B T$, energy of that quantum system decreases. Then according to equation no. (2), k also decreases. Reduction of k means increase of λ_{th} . But according to equation no. (5) increment of λ_{th} occurred by increment of adjacent area distance d in that quantum system. So, we see that by decreasing temperature of a quantum system, its energy decreases but size (volume) increases.

So, according to our proposal we can say that size (volume) and energy (also temperature) of a quantum system are inversely proportional to each other. This statement is compatible to the big bang theory and Bose-Einstein statistics.

C. Gravitation

Due to distribution of discrete areas of space, each basic Schrodinger wave $\Psi(x, t) = A \sin(kx - \omega t)$ has an associated Schrodinger wave $\Psi_{gr}(x', t) = A \sin(kx' - \omega t)$ having unit of m^2 in SI system. $\Psi_{gr}(x', t)$ travels in the direction of x' . There is an angular difference θ between x and x' . $\Psi_{gr}(x', t)$ follows all possible straight open paths. In a region of space due to travelling of $\Psi_{gr}(x', t)$ there exists a field F_{gr} . In that field the bellow relation is obeyed.

$$\frac{d^2[\Psi_{gr}(x', t)]}{dt^2} = G_{\Psi_{gr}} \frac{b\hbar \frac{1}{\partial[A \sin(kx - \omega t)]}}{r} \quad (26)$$

E. Black hole

$$G_{\Psi_{gr}} = \frac{r}{-\frac{bhT}{4\pi^2 A} \sec(kx - \omega t)} \times \frac{d^2[A \sin(kx' - \omega t)]}{dt^2} \quad (27)$$

$$G_{\Psi_{gr}} = \frac{r}{-\frac{bhT}{4\pi^2 A} \sec(kx - \omega t)} \times (-\omega)(-\omega)(-A \sin(kx' - \omega t)) \quad (28)$$

$$G_{\Psi_{gr}} = \frac{r}{-\frac{bhT}{4\pi^2 A} \sec(kx - \omega t)} \times \frac{-4\pi^2}{T^2} \times A \sin(kx' - \omega t) \quad (29)$$

$$G_{\Psi_{gr}} = \frac{-4\pi^2 A}{bhT} \times \frac{-4\pi^2 A}{T^2} \times r \times \cos(kx - \omega t) \sin(kx' - \omega t) \quad (30)$$

$$G_{\Psi_{gr}} = \frac{16\pi^4 A^2}{bhT^3} \times r \times \cos(kx - \omega t) \sin(kx' - \omega t) \quad (31)$$

Where,

r is the distance of a point of F_{gr} from the center of travelling region of $\Psi(x, t)$.

$G_{\Psi_{gr}}$ is a dynamic entity in x' direction. Time domain period and space domain period of $\cos(kx - \omega t) \sin(kx' - \omega t)$ is $T/2$ and $\lambda/2$ respectively.

In SI system unit of $G_{\Psi_{gr}}$ is $m^3 K g^{-1} s^{-2}$ which is same to the Newtonian gravitational constant G .

Hence, we want to declare here that F_{gr} is the quantum gravitational field.

In the *FIG.V.2* $\Psi(x, t)$ travels counterclockwise in a circular path having radius R . Angular difference (θ) between x and x' is 90° . Mass distribution along the circular path is m . So, according to our discussion, there exists a quantum gravitational field in the surrounding of the circular path.

In the region of space where $r > R$ if we connect the points of space having particular $\frac{d^2[\Psi_{gr}(x', t)]}{dt^2}$ we will find a closed circular line.

D. Redshift due to gravitation

Suppose an electromagnetic wave (a photon stream) travels from high gravitational field to low gravitational field. According to our hypothesis, along its travelling path $\frac{d^2[\Psi_{gr}(x', t)]}{dt^2}$ is high to low. So, area movement of a photon is affected by gradation of $\frac{d^2[\Psi_{gr}(x', t)]}{dt^2}$. At high $\frac{d^2[\Psi_{gr}(x', t)]}{dt^2}$ frequency of area movement of photon is higher than at low $\frac{d^2[\Psi_{gr}(x', t)]}{dt^2}$. Alternatively at high $\frac{d^2[\Psi_{gr}(x', t)]}{dt^2}$ wavelength of area movement of photon is lower than at low $\frac{d^2[\Psi_{gr}(x', t)]}{dt^2}$.

This is gravitational red shift.

A quantum system is possible in a region of space where the below relation is obeyed.

$$d_s \geq d_{min} \quad (32)$$

Where,

d_s is the distance between any two physically adjacent areas of space of a region.

d_{min} is the minimum distance between any two physically adjacent areas of space necessary for a quantum system.

A quantum system is not possible in a region of space where $d_s < d_{min}$ because in this region movement of an area of space is not possible due to insufficient inter area gap (d_s). Our so-called singularity appears in such a dense region of space.

We predict that the center region of black hole made of such dense space.

In *FIG.V.3*

$d_s < d_{min}$ in R region of space. No quantum system exists in this region. So, there is no mass in R . This is a so-called singular zone.

$d_s \geq d_{min}$ in K region of space. There is a finite but extreme amount of quantum systems in K . So, there is finite but extreme amount of mass in K .

S is the affected region of space due to the finite but extreme amount of quantum system in k . Finite but extreme gravitation exists in S .

If there is infinite mass in R then one black hole is enough to shrink the universe. But the universe exists though there are so many black holes in it. It indicates that proposal of zero mass in the center of black hole is valid.

This is the explanation of finite but extreme gravitation in the surrounding of a black hole.

F. Space-time constant in inertial reference frame

A distinguished movement of an area of space in a quantum system can be called a quantum event. In an inertial reference frame, there is a constant associated with each quantum event. It is as like-

$$S_T = \frac{d}{t} \quad (33)$$

Where, d is the distance crossed in space due to a quantum event. It is equal to the distance between any two adjacent areas which participate to create that quantum system, t is required time for a quantum event.

It should be noted here that d necessarily is not a distance between any two physically adjacent areas of space. It is a distance between any two areas of space which participate in creating the Schrodinger wave and adjacent in space domain Schrodinger wave.

FIG. V.2. For gravitation

FIG. V.3. For black hole

Due to inherent character of space, if d increases t also increases and vice versa.

Unit of S_T is ms^{-1} . So, it is also quantum event velocity in space. In a quantum system a quantum event moves from one area of space to the next area of space which participate to create that quantum system and thus Ψ of that quantum system is created. Hence, S_T is also the phase velocity of Ψ .

According to the special relativity theory in an inertial reference frame velocity of light (c) is constant in empty space. It indicates a characteristic constant in empty space for inertial reference frame.

From the view of quantum mechanics, we can say that in an inertial reference frame velocity of photon (c) is constant in empty space.

But we know that photon is a quantum system and

according to our hypothesis dynamics of a cluster of areas of space gives the notion of a photon.

Hence, we want to say here that indicated space constant in the theory of special relativity is nothing but our hypothesized S_T .

Unit of S_T and c says that they are the same element.

Briefly, constancy of light speed in empty space in an inertial reference frame is a fundamental character of space and c is a fundamental constant of empty space in an inertial reference frame.

S_T can be called also as a structural constant of empty space in an inertial reference frame.

G. Wave particle duality

Interaction between quantum system Y_1 and Y_2 means interactions among areas of Y_1 and Y_2 . Interaction may be in space domain (momentary) or in time domain (durational). We define two types of interaction as below.

Interaction in space domain means interaction occurred must in a single point of time domain but in more than one point of space domain. For interaction in space domain interaction length must be equal to the wavelength of Ψ of that quantum system under examination.

Interaction in time domain means interaction occurred must in a single point of space domain but in more than one points of time domain. For interaction in time domain interaction duration must be equal to the period of Ψ of that quantum system under examination.

Suppose we want to sense the nature (particle nature/wave nature) of Y_1 . To do this, we propose an equation to explain the nature (particle nature/wave nature) of a quantum system. It is-

$$\Delta d = d_{Y_1} - d_{Y_n} \quad (34)$$

Where,

d_{Y_1} is distance between adjacent areas of Y_1 .

d_{Y_n} is distance between adjacent areas of Y_n and Y_n is another quantum system using as testing tool. $n = 2, 3, 4, \dots$

Δd is difference between d_{Y_1} and d_{Y_n} .

It should be noted here that d necessarily is not a distance between any two physically adjacent areas of space. It is a distance between any two areas of space which participate in creating the Schrodinger wave and adjacent in space domain Schrodinger wave.

As illustrated in *FIG.V.4* we consider Y_1 and Y_n as the given notion by vibrating areas of space. We measure the area towards our right side as positive and towards our left side as negative.

Next, we discuss interaction in space domain and interaction in time domain separately using *FIG.V.4*.

1. Interaction in space domain

For interaction in space domain, we want to say that the more areas of Y_1 participate in the interaction the more wave nature of Y_1 and the less particle nature of Y_1 will be sensed. On the other hand, the less areas of Y_1 participate in the interaction the less wave nature of Y_1 and the more particle nature of Y_1 will be sensed.

If $\Delta d = 0$ probable alignment among areas of Y_1 and Y_n is such that in an interaction participation probability of maximum number of areas of Y_1 is 50% and participation probability of minimum number of areas of Y_1 is 50%. Hence, at this point probability of wave nature and particle nature of Y_1 for an interaction are 50% and 50% respectively.

If $\Delta d = \Delta d_w/2$ probable alignment among areas of Y_1 and Y_n is such that in an interaction participation probability of maximum number of areas of Y_1 is 75% and participation probability of minimum number of areas of Y_1 is 25%. Hence, at this point the probability of wave nature and particle nature of Y_1 for an interaction are 75% and 25% respectively.

If $\Delta d = \Delta d_w$ probable alignment among areas of Y_1 and Y_n is such that in an interaction participation probability of maximum number of areas of Y_1 is 100% and participation probability of minimum number of areas of Y_1 is 0%. Hence, at this point probability of wave nature and particle nature of Y_1 for an interaction are 100% and 0% respectively.

If $\Delta d_w < \Delta d \leq \Delta d_{Y_n(Planck)}$ probable alignment among areas of Y_1 and Y_n is such that in an interaction participation probability of maximum number of areas of Y_1 is 100% and participation probability of minimum number of areas of Y_1 is 0%. Hence, in this range probability of wave nature and particle nature of Y_1 for an interaction are 100% and 0% respectively. $\Delta d_{Y_n(Planck)}$ occurred when Y_n is in Planck length (the minimum possible distance in space).

If $\Delta d = -\Delta d_p/2$ probable alignment among areas of Y_1 and Y_n is such that in an interaction participation probability of maximum number of areas of Y_1 is 25% and participation probability of minimum number of areas of Y_1 is 75%. Hence, at this point probability of wave nature and particle nature of Y_1 for an interaction are 25% and 75% respectively.

If $\Delta d = -\Delta d_p$ probable alignment among areas of Y_1 and Y_n is such that in an interaction participation probability of maximum number of areas of Y_1 is 0% and participation probability of minimum number of areas of Y_1 is 100%. Hence, at this point probability of wave nature and particle nature of Y_1 for an interaction are 0% and 100% respectively.

If $-\Delta d_p > \Delta d \geq -\Delta d_C$ probable alignment among areas of Y_1 and Y_n is such that in an interaction participation probability of maximum number of areas of Y_1 is 0% and participation probability of minimum number of areas of Y_1 is 100%. Hence, in this range probability of wave nature and particle nature of Y_1 for an interaction are 0% and 100% respectively.

If $\Delta d < -\Delta d_C$ no interaction will occur between Y_1 and Y_n .

Participatory maximum number of areas of Y_1 is different for different Δd . Similarly participatory minimum number of areas of Y_1 is different for different Δd .

We want to say that $|\Delta d_w| = |\Delta d_p|$ and also want to call $(\Delta d_w - (-\Delta d_p)) = 2|\Delta d_w| = 2|\Delta d_p|$ as band of perfect dual character of Y_1 .

2. Interaction in time domain

For interaction in time domain no matter how many areas of Y_1 participate in the interaction but we need

FIG. V.4. Wave particle duality

only one interacting area of Y_1 to find out Y_1 nature. A participatory area of Y_1 gives the sense of wave nature of Y_1 . No particle nature of Y_1 can be sensed by this type of interaction.

VI. CONCLUSION

The stated area-time approach for a quantum (discrete) system is a different attempt to describe a quantum (discrete) system. Schrödinger wave function $\Psi(x, t)$ is derived from the dynamics of a cluster of quantized (discrete) areas of space. Mass and energy are expressed as different manifestations of area-time (space-time). Discussed dynamics indicate a quantum mechanical explanation of gravitation. Explanations of some physical issues using the proposed hypotheses mark the hypotheses as a first step to the theory of everything.

Data availability

This content is available in
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14739216>

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Declarations

The corresponding author states that there is no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] 'On a heuristic point of view concerning the production and transformation of light', by A. Einstein, *Annalen der Physik* 17 (1905) : 132-148
- [2] <https://einsteinpapers.press.princeton.edu/vol2-trans/100>
- [3] 'On the electrodynamics of moving bodies', by A. Einstein, *Annalen der Physik* 17 (1905) : 891-921
- [4] <https://einsteinpapers.press.princeton.edu/vol2-trans/154>
- [5] <https://history.aip.org/exhibits/einstein/voice1.htm>
- [6] 'The Foundation of the General Theory of Relativity', by A. Einstein, *Annalen der Physik* 49 (1916) : 769-822
- [7] <https://einsteinpapers.press.princeton.edu/vol6-trans/158>
- [8] C. Rovelli, L. Smolin, Discreteness of area and volume in quantum gravity, *Nucl. Phys. B* 442 (3), 593-619, 1995.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0550-3213\(95\)00150-Q](https://doi.org/10.1016/0550-3213(95)00150-Q).
[arXiv:gr-qc/9411005v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/gr-qc/9411005v1).